

INFLUENCE OF SUPERVISION ON TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE IN
PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ENUGU SOUTH
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF
ENUGU STATE.

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Abstract

This study was carried out to analyze the Influence of supervision on teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State. Descriptive survey research design will be used for this study. The area of the study was public secondary schools in Enugu south Local Government area of Enugu state. The population of the study consisted of 842 teachers in Enugu south local government area of Enugu state. Simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of 302 of which is 36% of the entire population. The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire. The analysis of the data was done using the mean and frequency. The findings from the study revealed that; teachers are reluctant to open-up to supervisors especially when any negative information may-be used against them, it curtails authentic interactions and productive problem solving because they hinder social support and distort communication of information. It also enables teachers to know their strength and weaknesses, it improves the entire teaching and learning situation, it stimulates, direct, guide and encourage the teachers to apply institutional procedures, techniques and principles and assists the teachers in solving educational problems it was recommended among others that The government should make provision of adequate funds, development and regular review of supervision tools.

Keywords: Supervision, Functions, Teacher and Public Secondary

Introduction

There are supervisors in every field of knowledge or professions. In education, supervision is centered on educational issues. Supervision is seen as all efforts of designated school officials toward providing guidance and leadership to teachers and other educational workers in the improvement of instruction. Supervision is an opportunity to bring someone back to their own mind, to show how good they can be. Instructional supervision according to Achibong, (2012) is an activity designed to improve instruction in School through

changing teacher behaviour in order to enhance and facilitate learning in a way that the goals of the organization are achieved. From these definitions, it can be deduced that a supervisor is one who monitors the activities of teachers in the classroom with the aim of providing professional guidance. The fundamental focus of instructional supervision is the input maximization of teaching and supporting staff for quality control of teaching and students learning activities. As such, supervision has two contexts such as the people and the improvement of the school programme

(Utaka 2012). She also added that the mediator between the people and the programme is the supervisor.

Supervision in education is very necessary so as teachers will not lose focus and start deviating from the main aim and objectives of the school. Supervision of schools in Nigeria started with the advent of the Christian missionaries who brought western education in 1842. Education in those days were mainly focused on teaching the locals basic literacy to aid evangelism. There was a problem of high recruitment of unqualified personnel because of great increase in the population of students in primary schools. That was why it became very imperative to help and guide those teachers in order to carry out their work effectively. Supervision in Nigeria became official when the British government announced the Education Ordinance in 1882 which stated the inauguration of an Inspectorate of Education for all British West African Countries. Instructional supervisory practices have steadily, over the years been transformed from “inspection” and “untrained” pupil-teachers by all knowing officials called Inspectors to the present day democratic and co-operative interchange between supervisor and supervisee. Suparto (2020) stated that Instructional supervision is one of the techniques by which school administrators seek to attain acceptable performance and results. It is a quality control tool in the school system and a phase of school administration that focuses primarily on the achievement of educational systems suitable expectations. Teachers whether new or experienced, require assistance in implementing educational programmes. As school heads, principals must provide this assistance to teachers, as well as be involved in the execution of instructional programmes by monitoring

what teachers are doing with students. These includes: classroom observation, personal interaction and instructional support. According to Suparto (2020) academic supervision combined with classroom observation techniques can increase teacher learning quality. He further added that the classroom observation comprises pre-determined indicators that have been agreed upon by the teachers and observers, guaranteeing that the teachers are prepared. Ghavifekr, Husain, Roden & Hamat (2019) stated that an effective supervision method, according to a related study, includes elements like pre-observation, planning, observation, implementation and post observation monitoring. Instructional support for teachers is a school leaders' method for maximizing individual teachers' success while also serving as a screening procedure for teachers who may require specialized education services. Darling-Hammond, Hylar & Gardner, (2017) highlighted that it is only through effective instructional supervision that the instructional supervisor can assist teachers to perform their duties in a better way. Instructional support is a positive and result oriented approach that enjoys particular evaluation and intervention techniques to assist all teachers in removing educational or behavioural stumbling blocks needed for their class instructions. Some scholars believe that the major aim of instructional supervision is to assist teachers to be conversant with their teaching and the impact it has on their learners (Osman & Mukano 2013).

It is important to state that supervision of instruction can only be said to be effective if it achieves its stated objectives, which is quality instructional delivery. Anything to the contrary means the failure of the programme of supervision (Eke

&Chinweuba, 2012). The tasks and responsibilities of a school principal, though often daunting, certainly include the assurance that excellence in teaching is the centerpiece of the teachers' agenda. Supervision of the instruction process is the quality control element of student learning, and teacher evaluation is an important element of that quality control, as well as an important element of effective leadership by the principal. When a teacher is performing in a marginally effective manner and principal does not confront the teacher with the problem, then the principal is also performing in a marginal manner. He further listed five reasons for school supervision as follow: It fosters the self-development of each teacher, it helps to identify a variety of tasks that the teacher is capable of performing, helps to identify self-development needs, helps to determine the placement, transfer or promotion of teachers and helps to determine the if a teacher should be retained in the division or district. The need to identify the influence of supervision of instruction on teachers to ensure they function effectively on the work assigned to them is the focus of this study.

Research Questions

1. Does the hierarchical differentiation in the status of Supervisors and Teachers on the performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State?
2. Does the usefulness of supervision on teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State?

Literature Review

Concept of Supervision

Supervision is a task in the educational setting that involves the leading and oversight of the instructional program as well as the responsibility for personnel evaluation. Throughout the history, influences and impacts on supervision included government involvement, scientific management, business management and practices and educational research and practices (Qurat-ul-ain, 2017). Wayne & Patrick (2019) defined Supervision of instruction as the set of activities designed to improve the teaching-learning process. He believed that the purpose of supervision is not to make judgments about the competence of teachers or to control them but rather to work cooperatively with them. It is also a process or an activity by which an individual, a group or team of individuals by means of advising and stimulating interest in teachers and students help to improve teaching and learning situation in educational institutions. This is to say in essence that instructional supervision makes positive impacts in education by helping teachers to improve on their teaching skills. Eya& Leonard (2012) defined a supervisor as anyone assigned the function of others (teachers) to improve on their instructional competencies.

Scope of Supervision

Supervision in Education touches so many areas which include instructional work, school environment, development of activities, records and registers, co-curricular activities, etc.

Instructional work: The first and foremost task of the supervisor is how to improve the instruction. For this, he supervises methods of teaching employed for different subjects, audio-visual aids used, time table, the distribution of work amongst teachers, the

written works of students and its correction, teachers lesson diaries and scheme of work.

Co-curricular Activities: the supervisor supervises the organization of various co-curricular activities keeping in view their needs and importance. These curricular activities are: Games and sports, dramatic arts, school magazines, library services, educational tours, field trips and picnics.

Records and Registers: the supervisor has to supervise all the records and registers of an educational institution or school by examining the following types of records: admission register, attendance register, the cash book, the log book, stock register and receipt book.

The School Environment: the school environment has a profound role bringing

over an improvement of educational process. For this, the supervisor has to supervise the following aspect of the school environment: school discipline, relationship between the staff and the students, cleanliness of the surroundings, plantation of trees, relationship among teachers, relationship between the head of the institution and the staff, etc.

Developmental Activities: the supervisor supervises the developmental activities of the school in the following heads: justification of developmental activities; proposals for the extension of the school building. Allotment receipt and the progress made: difficulties made and the steps taken by the headmaster to wipe out the difficulties and construction of the new buildings and its progress. (Diksha, 2012)

Distinction between supervision and inspection

The differences between supervision and inspection as outlined by Nwachukwu&Nanighe (2014) are summed in the table below.

	Inspection	Supervision
1	The aim of inspection is to find reasons for closing, opening or retaining a school	The aim of supervision is to help teachers and students to carry out the teaching and learning process more effectively.
2	School inspection is teacher and principal centered. The fundamental aim of inspection is to serve the purpose of witch-hunting.	Supervision is concerned with the general structure of the school system. It deals with anything from the school curriculum to the welfare of students and teachers.
3	Inspection rigidly stresses strict compliance to set down rules and regulations irrespective of peculiar local conditions, which may make some of the set of rules and regulations not workable.	Supervision looks at management variables such as plans, policies and programmes. In conjunction with other participants; supervisors' workout mutually accepted formula for supervision after considering all prevailing conditions in the school and immediate environment.
4	Inspection is normally not thorough because they are usually directed as specific occasional problems, such as	Supervision is usually well planned and it is not reserved for investigating occasional problems.

	investigating case of fraud.	
5	Inspection usually demand respect. They intimidate teachers, students and school heads	Supervisors earn respect by sharing expertise. They are considerate on matters they encounter during supervision.
6	Inspection is usually conducted by a person who is regarded as jack of all trade.	Supervision is usually teamwork that is characterized by division of labour. Expert advice is sort and obtained by teachers and students.
7	Inspection reports are usually not written immediately after supervision	Supervision reports are usually discussed with the teachers and students immediately
8	There is always lack of follow-up activities after inspection.	Follow-up activities normally commence at the earliest possible time.

Hierarchical differentiation in the status of Supervisors and Teachers

Wayn& Patrick (2019) highlighted that Supervisors are staff – master teachers. they are expected to provide advice and support to colleagues, not to discipline them. The staff position has little formal authority; authority is –primarily informal and earned arising from the supervisor’s expertise and personal skills. Teachers must have confidence in those to whom they turn for help, and trust can more readily be built when status distinctions among supervisors and teachers are limited. In fact, formal authority and status can be dysfunctional for supervisors as they seek to establish colleague relationships. Such status distinctions are likely to curtail authentic interactions and productive problem solving because, they hinder social support, restrict and distort communication of information.

He further added that social interaction and social support are inhibited by status. Individuals are more comfortable and secure interacting with people of similar status. Teachers do not need to hold back or worry about impressing their supervisors when they are colleagues with no formal control; however, the introduction of formal

authority into the supervisor –teacher relationship negatively affects the interactions. Teachers are reluctant to open up to superiors especially when any negative information may-be used against them. Subordinates are also more likely to impress their superiors often at the expense of colleague. It is not unusual for subordinates to communicate only information that will make them look good and please the supervisor or to hide the truth if it’s not positive. Furthermore, it is not easy to oppose superior. Most people think twice before questioning one with formal authority. Blau and Scott in Wayn (2017) argued that hierarchical differentiation in status impedes group problem solving by reducing social interaction and social support, by undermining the process of competition for respect, and by distorting information transmitted by individuals in different status positions. The very factors that enhance group problem solving are eroded by formal authority distinctions. Supervisors are part of the technical level in schools. As such they are concerned primarily with Teaching and learning; they are first and foremost teachers-masters teachers, not administrators. Their area of expertise is curriculum and instruction; their

job is to help their colleagues improve the teaching learning process. They need an organizational structure that allows them to do this in a nonthreatening environment. Unfettered by bureaucratic requirements for control. The improvement of instruction is a long-term continuous process. The goal of the supervisor is not simply to solve an immediate problem but rather to study the process of teaching and learning as part of an ongoing system of evaluation and experimentations.

The major functions of supervision

Inspection: the term refers to the study of existing school conditions. The first task of a supervisor is to survey the school system in order to discover problems or defects of the learners, teachers, equipment, school curriculum, objectives and methods of instruction, together with the conditions that surround them. Problems or defects may be discovered through actual observations, educational tests, conferences, questionnaires and check lists. Once discovered they should be classified into major and minor problems. The major defects should be formulated into supervisory objectives to be attained for the semester or for the year(s) of course. Inspection as a function must be based on actual facts.

Research: Pure research has its place in supervision as well as in science. The fundamental aim of this function is to formulate a plan to remedy the weakness or to solve the problem discovered. The supervisor should conduct research to discover means, methods and procedures fundamental to the success of supervision. The solutions discovered through research should be passed on to the teachers and other personnel connected with the school system. Teachers in the field should also be

encouraged to conduct their own research for self-development. Research, as a function should be practical and applicable to existing procedures and conditions.

Training: Acquainting the teachers with the solutions discovered or formulated through research is within the training function of supervision. Training may take the form of demonstration teaching, workshop, seminars, directed observation, individual or group conference, inter-visitation, professional classes, or the use of bulletins and circulars. Training function must be based on the democratic principles of supervision – respect for rights and opinion of others. Supervision must endeavour to keep up with the best prevailing standard of improving the total teaching learning situation.

Guidance: the concept of guidance has found expression in the field of school supervision. Guidance involves personal help given by someone. It is the function of supervision to stimulate, direct, guide and encourage the teachers to apply instructional procedures, techniques, principles and devices. Assisting the teacher to accomplish his purpose and to solve the problems that arise in his teaching is within the scope of guidance function. Guidance like training should be given in the spirit of democratic leadership.

Evaluation: this can be considered the ultimate major function of supervision. The purpose of evaluation is to appraise the outcomes and factors conditioning the outcomes of instruction and to improve the products and processes of instruction. This function calls for the use of educational tests and measurement. It is the duty of the supervisor to help develop an adequate instrument with which to measure the teaching –learning process and set up

standards of attainment as are necessary for the appraisal of the teacher's progress.

Models of supervision in education

- 1) clinical supervision
- 2) walk through supervision
- 3) differentiated model of supervision

Clinical supervision

Cogan in Aljhune 2017 defined clinical supervision as a vehicle for developing professional and responsible teachers who are capable of analyzing their own performance, who are open to change and assistance from others, and who are above all, self-directing. He also insists that the proper domain of clinical supervision is the classroom behaviour of the teacher, not the teacher as a person.

Walk through supervision

Walkthrough supervision according to Qurat-ul-ain, 2017 is an instructional supervision technique which is designed to help administrators and teachers to focus collaboratively on instructional practices and also to identify educator training and support needs. Walk through can last from 2 to 45 minutes. The observing group can range from 2 to 12 people and may include teachers, administrators, community members and students. This model focuses on just one teacher, all teachers or a sub-set of teachers and institution. It provides formative assessment data that answers the question, "how are we doing?" in regards to the implementation of standards-based teaching and learning. Examining and analyzing his data is a key practice of continuous improvement.

Do's' and don'ts for effective and quality supervision of instruction.

There are certain things supervisors should do away with for them to carry out effective

and quality supervision of instruction in secondary schools. In other words, they are those attitudes that hinder efficient supervision viz:

- 1) Supervision should not be seen and use as a means of clamping down on staff
- 2) Supervision should not be viewed as a fault-finding weapon.
- 3) Supervisors should not forcefully or autocratically take charge of the classroom instructional interaction from the teacher to prove a point.
- 4) Supervisors should avoid inspection.
- 5) Avoid evaluation of the school as designated place of learning.
- 6) Avoid acting as threats to teachers' careers.
- 7) Avoid authoritarian attitude in the conduct of supervision of instructions
- 8) Supervisors should see their roles as basically that of a facilitator.

Panaceas to effective supervision of instruction in secondary school.

Haven listed the factors that hinder effective supervision of instruction, it is more imperative to be abreast of the positive factors that enhance quality supervision of instruction in schools. They are:

- ❖ Enhanced satisfaction: the procedures of supervision should result in improved staff morale and job satisfaction. Thus, the supervision should help teachers to develop more confidence in themselves.
- ❖ Advice and guidance: the supervisors should help teachers to feel more adequate to handle their own problems and experience the fuller realization of their capabilities.
- ❖ Assistance: the instructional supervisor should assist teachers to see far beyond their immediate performance and strive

for quality improvement in instructional interactions.

- ❖ Cooperation: A genuine supervisor encourages the full participation of all those involved in the teaching and learning process rather than skill manipulation of staff. Thus, the effective

Theoretical Framework

Theory X

Mcgregor postulated this theory which states that there is no intrinsic satisfaction in work, that humans avoid work as much as possible

The major assumptions of this theory as summarized by Kombo&Oloko (2014) are shown in the table below.

	Assumption of theory X	Assumption of theory Y
1	People are generally gullible and not very sharp and bright	People want to assume responsibility
2	People lack ambition, dislike responsibility and prefer to be directed by others.	People have need for achievement.
3	People are inherently indifferent to organizational needs and goals.	People are not by nature passive or resistant to organizational goals.
4	People are by nature indolent; that is why they like to work as little as possible.	People want their organization to succeed.

Research Method

Descriptive survey research design will be used for this study. The area of the study will be public secondary schools in Enugu south Local Government area of Enugu state. The population of the study will consist of 842 teachers in Enugu south local government area of Enugu state. The sample will be 302. A simple random sampling

supervisor seeks the adoption of pre-conference, observation and post-conference to enable the teacher to be part and parcel of the decision reached.

- ❖ Supervision should help to increase the rate and quality of learning by students.

and positive direction to achieve the common objectives.

Theory Y

This theory explains a participative style of leadership and supervision.

technique will be used in the selection of 302 of which is 36% of the entire population. The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire. A research Assistant will be used to distribute the questionnaires to the respondents at a venue convenient for them. Duly completed questionnaires administered will be collected at the spot. The analysis of the data will be done using the mean and frequency.

Results

Research Question One

Hierarchical differentiation in the status of supervisors and teachers and the effect on teachers' performance in secondary schools.

Table 1: Means responses on the Hierarchical differentiation in the status of supervisors and teachers and the effect on teachers' performance in secondary schools.

S/N	Items	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	NO.	X	Dec.
		4	3	2	1			
1	Teachers are reluctant to open-up to supervisors especially when any negative information may-be used against them.	150	50	30	20	250	3.32	agree
		600	150	60	20			
2.	It curtails authentic interactions and productive problem solving because they hinder social support and distort communication of information.	50	50	130	20	250	2.52	agree
		200	150	260	20			
3.	Trust can be readily built when status distinctions among supervisors and are limited.	60	30	140	20	250	2.52	agree
4.	Teachers do not hold back or worry about impressing the supervisors when they are colleagues with no formal control.	140	50	40	20	250	3.40	agree
		560	150	120	20			
5.	Subordinates are also more likely to impress their supervisors often at the expense of their colleagues.	150	60	30	10	250	3.40	agree
		600	180	60	10			
Grand mean							3.00	

Findings in table 1 with a mean score of 3.32, 2.52, 2.52, 3.40, 3.40 showed that Hierarchical differentiation in the status of supervisors and teachers had effect on teachers' performance in secondary schools in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Research Question Two

Does the usefulness of supervision on teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State?

Table 2: Responses on the usefulness of supervision on teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State

S/N	Items	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	NO.	X	Dec.
		4	3	2	1			
6	Teachers abuse the students for answering a question wrongly.	70	130	30	20	250	3.00	agree
		280	390	60	20			

7	It enables teachers to know their strength and weaknesses.	150	50	20	30	250	3.28	agree
8	It improves the entire teaching and learning situation	140	50	40	20	250	3.24	agree
9	It stimulates, direct, guide and encourage the teachers to apply institutional procedures, techniques and principles	120	70	40	20	250	2.84	agree
10	Assists the teachers in solving educational problems	480	210	80	20			
Grand Mean							3.07	

The findings in table 2 from item 6-10 with mean score of 3.0, 3.28, 3.24, 2.84 and 3.0 shows that supervision is useful on teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

Findings in table one showed that; teachers are reluctant to open-up to supervisors especially when any negative information may-be used against them, it curtails authentic interactions and productive problem solving because they hinder social support and distort communication of information, trust can be readily built when status distinctions among supervisors and are limited and teachers do not hold back or worry about impressing the supervisors when they are colleagues with no formal control.

According to Ogunu (2011) the criteria for appointment of supervisor is basically the possession of a first degree in education and some years of teaching experience. He opined that in some cases, owing to acute shortage of supervisors, some teachers without the required level of education and teaching experience are recruited as supervisors thereby bringing a degrade in the level and performance of supervisors in secondary schools.

The findings in research question two showed that ;teachers abuse the students for answering a question wrongly, it enables teachers to know their strength and weaknesses, it improves the entire teaching and learning situation, it stimulates, direct, guide and encourage the teachers to apply institutional procedures, techniques and principles and assists the teachers in solving educational problems. The findings are in line with findings of Ochuba (2014) who stated that in order to keep abreast with current trends in supervision and innovation in the school system, there is need for appropriate training of inspectors throughout their career. He also noted that such workshops should be organized both at the state and zonal level to ensure continues capacity building of supervisors for effective performance. It becomes necessary now that the training opportunity is made available to teachers so that the inspectors do not become less qualified and experienced than those they inspect. The training should not be limited to skills acquisition but the observant of supervisors' code of conduct.

Conclusion

The study concluded that proper and regular supervision has the potential to promote schools effectiveness leading to the improvement of teacher effectiveness. From the responses of the teachers, the

study revealed that supervision stimulates, direct, guide and encourage the teachers to apply institutional procedures, techniques and principles.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the study.

1. The government should make provision of adequate funds, development and regular review of supervision tools.
2. Employment of qualified and experienced supervisors for effective performance of teachers.
3. Induction of new inspectors and capacity building for practicing inspectors and adequate legal provision for enforcing compliance by schools and proprietors.

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